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Introduction

The NERC Earth Observation Data Centre (NEODC) is the Natural Environment Research Council's Designated Data Centre for Earth Observation. The NEODC obtains and archives a variety of satellite and airborne remote sensing data and supplies this to the user community via its web site.

NEODC website

Users can register, search the NEODC catalogue and request access to datasets on the NEODC web site.

We welcome email enquiries about data and provide support once data has been supplied.

Satellite data

- ATSR-1/2 UBT products (ungridded brightness temperature)
- (A)ATSR Multimission Archive
ATSR-1 / ATSR-2 / AATSR in ENVISAT format
- ENVISAT data:
MERIS, GOMOS, SCIAMACHY, MIPAS
- Commercial satellite datasets:
LANDSAT, SPOT
- AVHRR FASIR adjusted NDVI and biological parameter fields
- MERIS MTCI (Terrestrial Chlorophyll Index)

Buncefield oil depot fire 11 Dec 05, AATSR visible and thermal image (CCLRC/ESA/DEFRA) and MERIS visible image (ESA)

Airborne data

- All data released by the NERC Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF) since 1982 (ATM, CASI and LiDAR)
- High resolution aerial photographs colocated with ATM and CASI data from the NERC ARSF
- Data from the SHAC2000 Synthetic Aperture Radar and Hyperspectral Airborne Campaign
- NEXTMap Britain digital elevation data, at a horizontal resolution of between 1.25 and 50 m.

ARSF ATM: Tamar Estuary

ARSF Aerial Photograph: Plymouth

Community and Projects

- NERC EO Centres of Excellence
Support to NERC CoEs with access to third party data, data distribution and long-term preservation of datasets of value to the wider community.
- NCAVEO
Support to the Network for Calibration and Validation of EO data with data dissemination to partners.
- Rothera ARIES AVHRR Archive
A searchable catalogue with preview images for the Rothera ARIES AVHRR archive at the NERC Remote Sensing and Data Analysis Service (RSDAS)

NCAVEO field experiment (photo: M.Steven)